

THE INFLUENCE OF THE INTERFACE ON DAMAGE DEVELOPMENT IN CFRP

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ABSTRACT

Composite materials need a good stress transfer between the fibres and the resin. Therefore, carbon fibres are surface treated. The influence of this surface treatment on the mechanical properties and the damage development in a cross ply $(0_2^{\circ}, 90_2^{\circ})_S$ carbon epoxy laminate during monotonic tensile testing was investigated. It is shown that the damage initiation is delayed by increasing the surface treatment time, while the damage growth rate strongly increases for higher treatment levels. For the mechanical properties, an optimum is reached at an intermediate treatment level.

INTRODUCTION

In today's industry, composite materials are becoming more and more important. This great interest in composite materials has resulted in research for new resins and new fibres. However, this has led to the fact that the interface has become very important for the mechanical properties of the composite^{1,2}.

In order to obtain a good load transfer between fibre and resin, good adhesion between fibre and matrix is necessary. According to Goan and Prosen³ the two predominant parameters for the adhesion between a fibre and the resin are:

- the surface roughness of the fibre;
- the surface tension of the two materials;

Although the surface roughness also contributes to the adhesion, the surface tension is the most important factor. It is influenced by the presence of chemically active groups on the surface of the fibre. Many authors^{4,5} have proved that an oxidative surface treatment increases the amount of chemically active groups on the fibre surface.

When the mechanical properties of these surface treated composites were tested, many authors focussed on ILSS testing. Only a few authors⁶ compared different surface treatment levels during real mechanical testing like monotonic tensile testing and impact. On the other hand, very little is known about the influence of the surface treatment level of the carbon fibres on the damage development in a real laminate. The goal of the research done at the Department of Metallurgy and Materials Engineering of the K.U. Leuven is to get a better understanding of the influence of the interface on the mechanical properties and the damage development in carbon fibre reinforced composites.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

1. Materials

All tests were carried out on crossply laminates with stacking sequence $(0_2, 90_2)_S$. The resin used for the tests was an epoxy resin HG9101 of Hysol Grafil Co. The mechanical properties are:

Tensile strength: 40 MPa
Tensile modulus: 3 GPa
Failure strain: 1.3 %

The fibre was an XA fibre of Hysol Grafil with the following mechanical properties:

Tensile strength: 3000-3300 MPa
 Tensile modulus : 220- 240 GPa
 Failure strain : 1.2-1.4 %

The fibres received an oxidative surface treatment. The duration of the treatment was varied in order to obtain different surface conditions:

100 %: the standard surface treatment of the XA fibres.

0 %: untreated fibres.

10 %: treatment time 10 % of the standard treatment.

400 %: treatment time four times the normal treatment time.

The surface treatment level has a great influence on the chemical activity of the fibre surface⁷. This causes an increase of the surface energy, as proved by Robinson et al.⁸. Due to a higher surface energy, the wetting of the fibre is improved and the active groups can form bonds with the resin.

2. Cure cycle

The (0°₂,90°₂)_S cross ply laminate was cured in a press at 175°C during 1 hour, after a heat-up period of 1 hour, with a pressure of 590 kPa. The overall fibre volume fraction was measured. It was 61 ± 1% for all specimens.

3. The testing procedure

The cured plate was cut into specimens which were tested on a tensile testing machine Instron 1196 (250 kN). The strain was measured with strain gauges.

The tests were performed incrementally with steps of 0.1 or 0.05% strain. Hence, the damage development can be investigated during the test, using the edge replication technique⁹ and penetrant enhanced radiography¹⁰.

A. The edge replication technique. To produce a replica of a polished edge, a piece of cellulose acetate tape is immersed and softened in acetone. The tape is subsequently pressed onto the specimen edge and allowed to harden. After removal the replica gives an exact copy of the edge of the specimen.

B. Penetrant enhanced radiography. It is not possible to use conventional radiography for carbon-epoxy laminates, because of the poor contrast due to the small difference in mass absorption coefficients between the defect (air) and the composite. Therefore, a liquid penetrant is used to improve the contrast. A Zinc Iodide based solution (60g ZnI₂ in 10 ml H₂O, 10 ml isopropanol and 10 ml Agfa Agepon) is applied. The specimen is submerged in the penetrant while it is still clamped in the testing machine. This is done by attaching a small, X-ray penetrant box over the specimen during testing. The box is filled with the penetrant and because the specimen is still in tension, the cracks are opened. This means that the solution can easily penetrate the cracks and delaminations.

RESULTS

Table 1. Mechanical properties of the (0°₂,90°₂)_S carbon-epoxy laminate in a tensile test. (E: tensile modulus; σ_m : tensile strength; ϵ_m : failure strain)

	E (GPa)	σ_m (MPa)	ϵ_m (%)
0 %	49	653	1.07
10 %	56	805	1.41
100 %	63	775	1.24
400 %	61	580	0.96

Fig. 1 Results of the edge replication technique: total crack length per mm specimen length as a function of the strain for the four different surface treatment levels.

In Table 1, the mechanical properties are listed. The stiffness increases up to 63 GPa at 100%, from where it remains almost constant.

For both failure stress and failure strain, a maximum is reached at about 10%, followed by an important decrease for higher surface treatment levels.

Fig. 1 presents the results of the edge replication technique. The crack length* is the largest for the specimens with untreated fibres, while the specimens with the

Fig. 2 Results of the in situ radiography: total crack length per mm² versus strain for the different treatment levels.

* After initiation, the cracks do not run through all the 90°-layers. They initiate in one layer and gradually grow over the entire thickness at higher strain levels. If the number of cracks is presented, this initiation process is neglected. Therefore, the crack length (in the thickness direction) is chosen.

standard treated fibres contain the lowest amount of cracks. In the specimens with the heavily treated fibres, there are no cracks until a strain level over 0.2% is reached. However, from that point on, the cracks nucleate and grow much faster than in the other samples.

The results from the radiography, presented in fig. 2, are about the same. However, the onset of crack growth is detected at higher strain values, compared with the results obtained by the edge replication technique.

DISCUSSION

1. Mechanical Properties.

These properties are strongly dependent of the 0°-plies. The influence of the fibre treatment on the mechanical properties has been discussed earlier by the authors¹¹.

2. Matrix cracking in the 90°-layers.

Fig. 1 and 2 show the results of the monitoring of damage in the 90°-layers: the crack initiation rate can be seen in fig. 1, while fig. 2 presents a combination of the two phenomena that determine the overall crack density: the initiation rate and the crack growth. Both are influenced by the interface properties.

Fig. 3 Photograph taken from the edge of a specimen with untreated fibres. The crack follows the interface. Debonding even occurs at other places than close to the crack.

A. Crack initiation becomes more difficult with increasing fibre treatment. The initiation of a crack in specimens with untreated fibres is expected to occur in the fibre rich zones. First, it is possible that there is no resin between the fibres. The thus created voids will then act as crack starters. Second, it is possible that a thin epoxy layer separates the fibres. Because of the low interface strength, debonding between the fibre and the resin will occur at a low strain level. Several debondings will then be linked by the fracture of the thin epoxy layers, which have to bear high stresses. This is shown in Fig.3. The weakness of the interface can be seen from the debonding which also occurs away from the crack.

It is obvious that a higher interface strength will make crack initiation more difficult. Initiation will also occur at matrix flaws.

B. Crack propagation. We must make a distinction between the crack growth in the thickness direction, and the growth parallel with the fibres. Cracks initiate at the deges of one of the four 90°-layers. Before groing inside the

laminate (in the width direction), they have to extend over the other 90°-layers in the thickness direction. This will be discussed first.

(a) Growth in the thickness direction. For specimens with untreated fibres, the growth mechanism is the same as the initiation mechanism: in front of the crack tip, debonding occurs. The crack grows when these debonds are linked by small matrix cracks (Fig.3).

At higher fibre treatment levels, the interface resists better to the stresses. Debonds do not occur so often in front of the crack tip. However, the stronger interface does not lead to pure matrix cracking: debonding still occurs (Fig.4). At other places, where the interface is strong and where the local geometry favours matrix cracking, no debonding is seen. This effect leads to a lower crack growth rate.

However, debonding has some positive influence on the crack growth rate. When a crack tip reaches a debonded fibre, the crack tip radius becomes equal to the fibre radius. This results in lower stress concentrations, and therefore the driving force for crack growth is lower. This effect decreases with increasing fibre treatment time, because debonding becomes more difficult. Therefore, especially in the specimens with severely treated fibres (400 %), the crack tip remains very sharp, resulting in high stress concentrations and a high crack growth rate. From Fig.5, it can be seen that the interface is very strong. The crack only follows the interface by coincidence (due to weak places at the interface). The specimens with severely treated fibres behave very brittle.

Fig. 4 Photograph taken of the edge of a specimen with standard treated fibres: the crack does not always go through the matrix. At some places, fibre splitting occurs.

(b) Growth parallel with the fibres. Once a crack has grown through the thickness, it will start growing in the width, parallel with the 90° fibre direction. Fig.2 presents the results of the latter growth direction. It shows the same tendency as Fig.1. However, since the crack grows in the fibre direction, this results in a somewhat different growth mechanism.

In the case of specimens with untreated fibres, the crack mainly follows the interface. Because the interface is weak, this does not consume a lot of energy. This means that, for the same amount of elastic energy stored in the specimen, the total crack length increment will be high for the untreated specimens. One might expect that, because of this, surface treatment will lower the crack growth rates. This is the case for low treatment levels. For high treatment levels however, the crack

growth rate increases.

This is caused by a second phenomenon. In specimens with untreated fibres, zones with a lot of resin will be avoided by the crack (because the resin is too strong). This results in a very capricious crack path. At higher treatment levels, the difference in strength between interface and resin becomes smaller, resulting in a more straight shaped crack. The total crack area, and thus the energy absorbed by crack growth, decreases. The consequence is that, for severe fibre treatments, the cracks will grow faster.

Fig. 5 Photograph taken of the edge of a specimen with severely treated fibres (400 %). The crack is straight and at some places, fibre splitting occurs.

4. Fibre splitting.(Fig.4,5)

in the specimens with highly treated fibres (100 and 400%), another phenomenon occurs: whereas the resin is thought to be the weakest element in the structure now, it appears that not only matrix cracking occurs, but also fibre splitting is detected. If a crack arrives at a strong interface, it is not blunted. This creates a very important stress field in the carbon fibre. These stress concentrations can pull two graphite layers (which are bonded by Van der Waals forces) apart if the orientation of the crystal planes is more or less parallel with the crack.

CONCLUSIONS

Fibre treatment is necessary to obtain a homogeneous laminate and to have a good interface. However, a strong interface is not always favourable, due to the embrittlement of the composite. A very light surface treatment is favourable. Even when the interface is strong, it does not mean that cracks no longer follow the interface. When damage development is modelled, the strength of the interface should always be taken into account.

Another important, damage phenomenon (next to fibre fracture, matrix cracking, debonding and delamination) is detected, namely fibre splitting, which occurs at higher treatment levels.

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